

Fearmaga

Federation of Sawmills and Timber Finishers

Fearmaga is a non-profit sector organization that defends the interests of small and medium-sized timber companies in Galicia, Spain. They promote the recycling of mussel farms after 25 years of use on the sea.

Highlights of innovative features

- The mussel farms, 20x20m rafts of bare eucalyptus beams, create substantial added value and sequester carbon for 25 years floating on the sea.
- These rough conditions create a very sought-after surface aspect of the beams that are delicately recovered to create high added value furniture in the 2nd use period of the wood.
- The long life-cycle of these products connects local SME based value chains and therefore contributes to social cohesion and cultural identity.

In Galicia, the wood industry is closely connected to the sea industry. “MareMonte” is a documentary highlighting this connection on the example of the life cycle of eucalyptus beams from rafts of mussel farms to a new use as beams in construction or rehabilitation, interior design, hotel and garden furniture, fences and gates.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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